

A Robust Open Framework Formed by Decavanadate Clusters and Copper(II) Complexes of Macrocyclic Polyamines: Permanent Microporosity and Catalytic Oxidation of Cycloalkanes

Jagoba Martín-Caballero,[†] Ana San José Wéry,[‡] Santiago Reinoso,[§] Beñat Artetxe,^{†,§} Leire San Felices,^{||} Bouchra El Bakkali,[⊥] Guido Trautwein,[⊥] Juan Alcañiz-Monge,[⊥] José Luis Vilas^{*,†,‡,#} and Juan M. Gutiérrez-Zorrilla^{*,†,§}

[†]BCMaterials, Parque Tecnológico de Bizkaia, Edificio 500, 48160 Derio, Spain.

[‡]Departamento de Desarrollo Sostenible, Universidad Católica de Ávila, c/Canteros s/n, 05005 Ávila, Spain.

[§]Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Facultad de Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad del País Vasco UPV/EHU, P.O. Box 644, 48080 Bilbao, Spain.

^{||}Servicios Generales de Investigación SGIker, Facultad de Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad del País Vasco UPV/EHU, P.O. Box 644, 48080 Bilbao, Spain.

[⊥]Grupo de Materiales Carbonosos y Medio Ambiente, Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Alicante, P.O. Box 99, 03080 Alicante, Spain.

[#]Departamento de Química Física, Facultad de Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad del País Vasco UPV/EHU, P.O. Box 644, 48080 Bilbao, Spain.

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Figure S1. FT-IR spectra of **1** compared with those of the $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{CNH}_3][\text{VO}_3]$ and $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{CNH}_3]_4[\text{H}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}] \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ precursors.

Figure S2. Details of the inorganic region in the FT-IR spectra of **1** compared with those of the $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{CNH}_3][\text{VO}_3]$ and $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{CNH}_3]_4[\text{H}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}] \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ precursors. The intense band corresponding to the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{V-O}_t)$ vibration that appears at 960 cm⁻¹ remains virtually unaltered compared to the decavanadate precursor, whereas the signal located at 983 cm⁻¹ and associated with the antisymmetric stretching vibration of protonated V-O_b bonds can no longer be found in the spectrum of **1**. This fact confirms that no basic oxygen atoms are protonated. The peak of medium intensity observed at 883 cm⁻¹ could not be assigned to other than the $\delta(\text{R-NH-R})$ vibration of the cyclam ligands. The signals at 835 and 748 cm⁻¹ are attributable to the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{V-O}_b\text{-V})$ mode, whereas those spanning from 594 to 532 cm⁻¹ correspond to the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{V-O}_b\text{-V})$ vibration. The poorly defined peaks corresponding to the $\nu_s(\text{V-O}_b\text{-V})$ vibration mode appear in the range 459 and 410 cm⁻¹.

Figure S3. Comparison between the experimental powder X-ray diffraction pattern of **1** and that simulated from single-crystal X-ray diffraction data.

Figure S4. Experimental powder X-ray diffraction pattern (left) and FT-IR spectrum (right) of the brown precipitate obtained from the reaction of VO_3^- and $\{\text{Cu}(\text{cyclam})\}^{2+}$ complexes in water (pH 4.6–4.7) compared to those of compound **1** in crystalline form. Arrows highlight the signals corresponding to impurities of the bulk material.

Figure S5. Identification by powder X-ray diffraction of the phases forming the final residue in the thermal decomposition of compound **1**.

Figure S7. {Cu(cyclam)} complexes in compound **1** (left) and possible configurations of the cyclam ligand in transition metal complexes (right); color code: Cu (blue), N (green), H (pink); hydrogen atoms are omitted except those connected to N atoms.

Figure S8. Structural relationship between the hybrid layers in **1** and those described for $(\text{Hpz})_2[\{\text{Cu}(\text{pz})_4\}_2(\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28})]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (pz = pyrazole). See the following reference for more information: Thomas, J.; Agarwal, M.; Ramanan, A.; Chernova, N.; Whittingham, M. S. *CrystEngComm* **2009**, *11*, 625–631.

Figure S9. Comparison of the hybrid layers in **1** and **1a**; color code: V (orange), Cu (blue), N (green), O (red); hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Symmetry codes: i) $2-x, 1-y, -z$; ii) $x, y, 1+z$; iii) $2-x, 1-y, 1-z$; iv) $x, -1+y, 1-z$; v) $2-x, -y, 1-z$; vi) $x, -1+y, z$; vii) $2-x, -y, -z$.

Figure S10. Distance between sandwiching decavanadate clusters and the Cu1A complex in **1** (left) and **1a** (right).

Figure S11. Comparison of the crystal packing in **1** with that of **1a**; color code: V (orange), Cu (blue), N (green), O (red); hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Symmetry codes: i) $2-x, 1-y, -z$; ii) $2-x, 1-y, 1-z$; iii) $x, y, 1+z$; iv) $-1+x, y, 1+z$; v) $1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; vi) $-1+x, y, z$; vii) $1-x, 1-y, -z$.

Figure S12. Comparison of the porous framework and the channels in **1** (left) and **1a** (right).

Table S1. V–O bond lengths (Å) of the decavanadate clusters in **1** and **1a**.

	1	1a
V1–O1	1.620(4)	1.619(3)
V1–O13	1.816(4)	1.805(3)
V1–O15	1.834(4)	1.825(3)
V1–O1C	1.971(4)	2.002(2)
V1–O12	1.998(4)	2.013(2)
V1–O2C	2.235(3)	2.224(2)
V2–O2	1.626(4)	1.613(3)
V2–O25	1.820(4)	1.813(2)
V2–O16 ⁱ	1.812(4)	1.832(3)
V2–O1C	2.013(3)	1.995(2)
V2–O12	1.996(4)	2.013(3)
V2–O2C ⁱ	2.232(3)	2.235(2)
V3–O3	1.608(4)	1.595(3)
V3–O16	1.871(4)	1.850(3)
V3–O35	1.827(4)	1.858(2)
V3–O13	1.858(4)	1.872(3)
V3–O34	2.061(4)	2.024(3)
V3–O2C	2.318(3)	2.367(2)
V4–O24	1.699(4)	1.680(3)
V4–O34	1.694(4)	1.702(2)
V4–O1C	1.918(4)	1.919(2)
V4–O12 ⁱ	1.939(4)	1.925(3)
V4–O2C	2.111(3)	2.070(2)
V4–O2C ⁱ	2.122(3)	2.169(2)
V5–O5	1.613(4)	1.620(3)
V5–O35 ⁱ	1.839(4)	1.807(3)
V5–O15 ⁱ	1.880(4)	1.861(3)
V5–O25	1.869(4)	1.881(3)
V5–O24	2.031(4)	2.098(3)
V5–O2C ⁱ	2.301(3)	2.281(2)

Symmetry code: i) 2–x, 1–y, –z.

Table S2. Comparison of the intermolecular N–H···O and C–H···O Interactions in **1** and **1a**.

Donor–H···Acceptor	1				1a		
	D–H (Å)	H···A (Å)	D···A (Å)	D–H···A (°)	H···A (Å)	D···A (Å)	D–H···A (°)
Complex Cu1A							
N1A–H1A···O12 ⁱ	0.98	2.36	3.177(6)	140	2.40	3.184(4)	137
N1A–H1A···O16 ⁱⁱ	0.98	2.24	3.111(6)	148	2.16	3.043(4)	149
N1A–H1A···O34 ⁱⁱ	0.98	—	—	—	2.57	3.259(4)	128
N4A–H4A···O12 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.98	2.50	3.266(6)	135	2.44	3.228(4)	137
N4A–H4A···O15 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.98	2.11	3.015(6)	153	2.14	3.040(4)	151
N4A–H4A···O24	0.98	2.56	3.233(7)	126	—	—	—
C6A–H6AB···O12 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.97	2.58	3.367(8)	138	2.56	3.339(5)	138
C3A–H3AA···O3 ⁱⁱ	0.97	2.39	3.289(8)	153	2.51	3.306(6)	140
C3A–H3AA···O34 ⁱⁱ	0.97	2.55	3.280(7)	132	2.44	3.190(5)	134
C2A–H2AA···O5	0.97	2.46	3.299(7)	144	2.46	3.298(7)	144
C6A–H6AA···O2 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.97	—	—	—	2.51	3.295(6)	138
C6A–H6AB···O1 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.97	2.52	3.342(8)	142	2.52	3.342(7)	142
C2A–H2AA···O24	0.97	2.51	3.227(7)	131	2.51	3.227(7)	131
C3A–H3BA···O7W ⁱⁱⁱ	0.97	2.57	3.441(15)	149	—	—	—
C6A–H6AB···O12 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.97	2.58	3.367(8)	138	2.56	3.339(5)	138
Complex Cu1B							
N1B–H1B···O35 ^{iv}	0.98	2.15	3.032(5)	149	1.85	2.812(5)	166
N4B–H4B···O25 ^v	0.98	1.91	2.846(5)	159	1.87	2.827(5)	165
N1B–H1B···O9W ^{iv}	0.98	2.58	3.308(13)	131	—	—	—
C5B–H5BA···O5	0.97	2.58	3.185(6)	121	2.57	3.171(6)	120
C2B–H2BB···O9W ^{iv}	0.97	2.60	3.209(13)	121	—	—	—
C6B–H6BB···O35 ^{iv}	0.97	2.55	3.360(7)	141	—	—	—
C6B–H6BA···O16 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.97	2.45	3.399(6)	167	2.45	3.399(6)	167
Complex Cu1C							
N1C–H1C···O13	0.98	2.11	2.949(6)	142	1.93	2.813(5)	148
N4C–H4C···O2	0.98	2.09	2.976(6)	149	2.18	3.040(5)	146
C3C–H3CA···O13	0.97	2.33	3.107(7)	136	2.50	3.211(7)	130
C3C–H3CA···O2	0.97	—	—	—	2.59	3.288(5)	129

Symmetry codes: i) $-1+x, y, z$; ii) $1-x, 1-y, -z$; iii) $2-x, 1-y, -z$; iv) $x, y, 1+z$; v) $2-x, 1-y, 1-z$; vi) $2-x, -y, -z$.